
The Concept of Culture in English Philosophy

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ABSTRACT: The culture is the dominant concept in English philosophy making it one of the most spreaded carriers of culture in the world. The representatives of British (mainly English) still continue to lead the global tendencies of literature, culture, arts and science. The Victorian Britain was the initiator of the first trends of the concept which is now named as the globalization. This epoch is characterized by the rapid changes in Iron, Ornament and Architecture in Victorian Britain. Despite its underrepresented in the population of the world the people from England hold second number after the representatives of US in the number of Nobel prize holders.

KEYWORDS: British humour, culturology, distance, etiquette, Nobel prize, philosophy, pluralism, privacy, renaissance

INTRODUCTION

The culture of England has a rich history and is associated with the heritage of such ancient European peoples as the Celts, Germans and Scandinavians. Anglo-Saxon culture had a huge impact on neighboring states, but also stepped far beyond the British Isles, becoming the basis for the globalized culture of the USA, Canada, Australia and many other countries of the world. The highest achievement of the culture of England today, without a doubt, can be considered the generally recognized giving the English language the status of the language of international communication. Since the end of 18th till the beginning of the 20th century British Empire being the main powerhouse of the world impacted the lifestyles of most countries of the world. In 2003 the BBC carried out a UK survey entitled *The Big Read* in order to find the "nation's best-loved novel" of all time, with works by English novelists J.R.R. Tolkien, Jane Austen, Philip Pullman, Douglas Adams and J. K. Rowling making up the top five on the list.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This article is conducted about the culture, philosophy, manners and customs of the English people; It introduces the traditions and cultures of England.

And, in my opinion, this article will prove to be an indispensable assistant for those who are going to travel abroad.

DISCUSSION

"Culture (from Lat. Cultura - cultivation, upbringing, education, development, veneration) is a set of artificial orders and objects created by people in addition to natural, learned forms of human behavior and activity, acquired knowledge, images of self-knowledge and symbolic designations of the surrounding world.

Philosophy of Culture - a section of theoretical cultural studies, which explores the concept, essence and structure of culture, determines its function in society. Cultural studies as a science arose in the middle of the twentieth century, however, as a separate branch of knowledge, it began to form at the end of the nineteenth century, by separating it from the philosophy of culture. Therefore, the philosophy of culture performs methodological functions in relation to cultural studies, this is its foundation, basis, the first section of theoretical cultural studies. The term "philosophy of culture" was first introduced at the beginning of the 19th century by German philosopher A. Müller[1].

Philosophy of culture is "designation of approaches to the study essence, goals and values of culture, its conditions and forms of manifestation. It has a huge number of forms and often turns out to be identical to the philosophy of history, since it is history that is considered as the process of unfolding and embodying the meaning of culture"[2].

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Every culture is different. It has its own mentality, its own system of truth and knowledge, its own philosophy and worldview, the type of religion and standards of "holiness", forms of art and literature, rules of morality and codes of conduct, its own economy and politics, laws and system of punishment.

In addition, in the spiritual part, many cultures can be quite close to each other, while in the interactional part, these same cultures reveal serious differences (cf. British and American culture, the culture of Germany and Austria). That is why cultural specificity should be traced not only in the material and / or spiritual, but also in the interactional, that is, in how the joint activities of people are organized to achieve a certain goal [3].

British civilization is a separate world, formed on the basis of the traditions of the peoples who inhabited the numerous islands, regions and provinces of the United Kingdom. It is a multicultural state with sovereignty over 14 overseas territories and 3 crown lands.

The lands of the British Isles were conquered by the Celts, Normans, Saxons, Vikings and Romans with varying success. The ethnic composition is very diverse. Culturally, there is a similar diversity. Therefore, here they are very tolerant of any religion and national traditions. English customs and traditions related to etiquette. There is a special custom associated with the dating procedure. According to the rules accepted in English society, someone else should introduce you and introduce you to each other.

In the culture of continental Europe there is a tendency towards Unity, monism in religion, philosophy, and worldview as a whole (Catholicism, patriotism, socialism ...), in England there is a cult of privacy (privacy): "my home is my fortress". The Englishman wants to define himself - in faith, in ideas, and in the style of life and way of life. There is no norm of a human character, on the contrary, multiplicity and diversity are honored.

In the second half of the 14th century in England, early humanistic tendencies were born, they mainly concerned literature and manifested themselves in the work of Geoffrey Chaucer (1340-1400). In the same period, the ideas of the early Reformation, formulated by J. Wycliffe, appeared. However, the rise of the 14th century was followed by a decline that lasted almost three quarters of a century. The rise of English culture was outlined in the late 15th century after the end of the civil war. The accession of the new Tudor dynasty and the strengthening of the monarchy created the preconditions for the formation of a national state and language. The formation of the national English culture took place against the background of close contacts with the countries of Western Europe, which contributed to the increasingly widespread dissemination of humanistic ideas in the 15th century.

In the development of the Renaissance culture of England, it is possible to distinguish the following stages:

- late 14th - late 15th century - Pre-revival;
- late 15th - first half of the 16th century - the period of the early Renaissance, the formation of a Renaissance culture on English soil;
- second half of the 16th century. - mature Renaissance, the era of the highest flowering of English culture;
- the beginning of the 17th century. - late Renaissance.

The originality of the English Renaissance is largely determined by the strong rise of the medieval folk theater, on the basis of which a dramatic tradition arose that won world fame.

The culture of the English Renaissance remained in history largely thanks to Shakespeare. The plays of William Shakespeare (1564-1616) entered the repertoire of the world theater and to this day occupy one of the first places in the posters. The device of the theater, for which Shakespeare wrote, the so-called "Elizabethan scene" (named after the queen who reigned at that time) for many years became an example and a model organization of the internal theater space, the subject of controversy and imitation.

The English principle of pluralism affects all areas. At the same time, the plural and the different are clothed in culture in separate, particular forms of existence. It has long been known that the British are united only by war. In everyday life, however, everyone is assigned their own place, their own "island" in the general system of forms of existence. First of all, this refers to the structure of society. According to English tradition, society should be divided into three main classes. In the old days, these were aristocrats, merchants and workers. Over time, due to the growth of the merchant class, the middle class became dominant and began to be divided into upper, middle and lower. But in the last quarter of the 20th century, society was divided into five main social groups, designated in order by the letters of the alphabet: the upper echelons with the letters AB, and the middle ones with the letters BC. The lowest stratum is also subdivided into groups D and E. Such a strict division of society speaks of the importance for the British of the issue of social status and the desire to give everything an appropriate place.

The Englishman perceives his class as a very large club of which he is a member.

The British achieve enrollment in one class or another with the help of various complex maneuvers and feel quite comfortable getting into these closed groupings. From a psychological point of view, their behavior and style should make an impression on others that is characteristic of their social level. It is very important for an Englishman to feel like a member of a

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social group. This is why there is such a commitment to the clubbing community here. Many of them were created for scientific or academic purposes - the Jane Austen Society, the Institute for Psychical Research, The Sealed Knot, which recreates the famous battles of the civil wars of 1642-1646, the Society for the Prevention of Unplanned Flights over the Atlantic. There are also societies of various collectors and enthusiasts - the Society of Ephemera (Annuals), the Society of Artistic Sawing, and the British Society of Button Collectors. In the club, an Englishman feels comfortable, having the opportunity to communicate in a closed environment and feel the kinship of souls.

At the same time, every person in this culture considers the right to preserve "private space" as important. Every inhabitant of England is his own island, "in his castle, the king", and he does not allow any invasion of his own borders [4].

As noted above, English-speaking cultures are characterized by a high degree of individualism, a large horizontal distance and a small vertical distance. Equality (egalitarianism) and distance are valuable. This is manifested in the use of space - the distance between people in the process of communication. E. Hall distinguishes 4 types of distance:

intimate - characterizes the distance between close people speaking in a whisper (E. Hall calls the number from 18 inches to touch);

personal - the distance of the handshake, at which close people (for example, spouses), being in a public place, speak softly (from 18 inches to 4 feet, i.e. from 45 to 120 cm);

social (casual) - the distance between colleagues, between the seller and the buyer, etc., speaking in full voice (4-12 feet - 120-360 cm);

public - the distance between the speaker and the audience, suggests loud speech (often using sound reinforcement) (more than 12 feet or 360 cm) [5].

The most important role in interpersonal communication is played by personal or personal distance. E. Hall figuratively calls it bubble (bubble), in different cultures its size varies, it is greatest, respectively, in distant ones. For English-speaking cultures, the value of personal distance, or personal space, is so high that there is a special concept - privacy - to denote it. This zone of personal autonomy manifests itself in the daily life of the British. When observing them, it becomes obvious that privacy is not an abstract concept, it is an objective reality visible to the eye. It may seem that there is an invisible circle around people that repels people as soon as they approach - they demonstrate the subtlest sense of distance.

The ideal of an Englishman is a gentleman - a person who depends only on himself. Self-restraint and restraint, self-control and self-suppression are important principles for him. The consequence of this is self-respect and the right to irony. The gentleman believes that the highly intelligent claims of the intellect should also be limited. He prefers to find his way by instinct, through inner sensations, but not by the logical chain of deduction. We find ironically recreated images of gentlemen in the "Pickwick Papers" by Charles Dickens.

If a person in critical situations shows a restrained sense of humor - this is typical in English and makes it possible to protect your inner world from the invasion of other people's influences. **British humour** carries a strong element of satire aimed at the absurdity of everyday life. Common themes include sarcasm, insults, self-deprecation, taboo subjects, puns, innuendo, wit, and the British class system [6]. These are often accompanied by a deadpan delivery which is present throughout the British sense of humour [7].

Ben Johnson has developed a whole theory of humor, and in English literature there are many variations and discoveries in this genre from Sheridan and Dickens to Oscar Wilde and Bernard Shaw. The image of the FOOL, the JESTER is the most important character in the English theater (the Jester in King Lear).

The important concepts of the English value system are common sense, practicality and moderation, which are expressed in their extreme foresight and determine the reluctance of the English to make at least one mistake, to make at least one wrong step. The Englishman often follows the rule - "You should always be prepared for any twists of fate". Every planned event should always have an alternative option in case" the worst happens.

Unlike the Frenchman, the Englishman is inclined not so much to think as to act, so he does not strive to seek higher and final truths and thinks about what he can really do. It is no coincidence that the aphorism "knowledge is power" was proclaimed by F. Bacon, while the Frenchman R. Descartes sought truth in the abstract principle "I think-therefore I am" [8].

The English mind does not trust the rules of logic and absolute truths, does not attack the problem "head-on", but, as it were, "flows around" from all sides. It is prone to empiricism, to inductive conclusions from the particular to the general. Bacon, Darwin, Sherlock Holmes are inductive thinkers. Therefore, parties strictly adhering to any doctrine do not enjoy influence in England. And English writers pay little attention to the systematic and logical nature of the story. Their books are often cumbersome, full of everyday details, describe life epic, in every detail. A typical example of such classical English literature is the novels of Charles Dickens and W. Thackeray.

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Science and philosophy occupy an important place in the general cultural system of England. Practice, experience, experiment and technique are key symbols of English thinking that explain the dominant importance of science as a way of exploring the world.

Since the era of the English bourgeois revolution and the industrial revolution, England has provided the world with many outstanding scientists in the fields of physics, chemistry, astronomy, medicine, philosophy and genetics.

British philosophy has a very long, literally centuries-old tradition. Its origins are in the Middle Ages and are associated with the names of Iona Scott Eriugena, the Irish philosopher, and Anselm of Canterbury, the founding philosopher of scholasticism. One of the most popular philosophers of the 20th century is Bertrand Russell, known for his works related to the defense of pacifism, atheism, and leftist trends in politics.

In the 14-15th centuries. - W.Hilbert explores geomagnetism. Hilbert was the first in England to support the heliocentric teachings of Copernicus and the conclusion of Giordano Bruno that the sun is only one of the countless stars in the universe. Gilbert died in London (or Colchester) on November 30, 1603.

Thomas More became the founder of utopian socialism. Among the topics discussed by More in *Utopia* were penology, state-controlled education, religious pluralism, divorce, euthanasia, and women's rights. The resulting demonstration of his learning, invention, and wit established his reputation as one of the foremost humanists. Soon translated into most European languages, *Utopia* became the ancestor of a new literary genre, the utopian romance [9].

Isaac Newton's discovery of the law of universal gravitation became the foundation of the European mechanistic picture of the world until the end of the 19th century. Newton made seminal contributions to several other scientific disciplines. In his book the Principia or "Mathematical Principles of Natural Philosophy, «which was published in 1687, Newton formulated the laws of motion and universal gravitation and is considered to have laid the foundations for classical mechanics. He also introduced the notion of a Newtonian fluid, studied the speed of sound, and developed an empirical law of cooling among other major contributions made to scientific discovery. Newton's image appeared on the Bank of England notes for about 10 years in the 1970s and 1980s. He has also been commemorated on various stamp and coins [10].

F. Bacon is responsible for the creation of an inductive way of thinking; Francis Bacon (1561 -1626) - English philosopher and statesman. Graduated from Cambridge University and Law School.

Although most of Bacon's life (and with a different approach, the whole) proceeded within the conditional chronological framework of the Renaissance, due to the nature of his teachings, he is considered the first philosopher of modern times.

J.Locke developed an empirical theory of knowledge; In England, the philosophy of culture is represented by the names of John Locke and John Toland. The first-rate figure among the English enlighteners was J. Locke (1632-1704), who developed the ideological and political doctrine of liberalism. According to the principles of "natural law", a person, according to Locke, has inalienable rights. This is the right to life, liberty and property. At the same time, Locke believed that the property of each person is the result of his labor.

Like most educators, Locke, in his understanding of society, proceeded from the recognition of the private interests of individuals. Law, according to Locke, must ensure the possibility of gaining benefits for everyone, without violating the freedom and private interests of everyone else [11].

Here are the some samples of English culture.

A taste of Britain	English clubs, theatres, shops and cinemas around the world
April fool	Just fooling around.
Bank holidays	What is a bank holiday?
Bog snorkeling	Yes. Snorkeling through a bog. Try it! You might like it!
Bonfire night	A penny for the guy?
British elections	There are five types of elections in the United Kingdom.
British houses	What is a typical British house like? This might surprise you.
British humour	Much is made about the British sense of humour, but what kind of humour do you mean?
British pop music	How much do you know about British pop music? Oh and by the way "The Beatles" don't count!
British television	British Television is famous (rightly or wrongly) around the world.

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Burns' night	Robert Burns is Scotland's favourite son and champion of the common people. Each year on January 25, the great man's presumed birthday, Scots everywhere take time out to honour a national icon.
Buying a house	Making money on property is almost a national pastime nowadays, but buying a house in the UK leads to lots of new vocabulary - gazumping, mortgages, equity and lots more explained here.
Candlemas(s)	A Pagan or Christian celebration.
Christmas	Christmas celebrations.
Clothes	Fashion and national costumes in the UK.
Cricket	One of the most popular sports in Britain.
Easter	Who is the Easter Bunny?
Edinburgh festival	One of the largest festivals in the world.
Education	The education system in the UK.
Food	Food in the UK, from the Great British Breakfast to Bangers and Mash and of course Cheese!
Food facts	20 quirky food facts.
Formal eating	Manners maketh the man!
Business lunches	Clinching the deal can sometimes mean doing the right thing over lunch.
Garden parties	By invitation only.
Glorious 12th	Not so glorious for the birds though.
Good friday	Commemorating the crucifixion of Jesus Christ.
Goose fair	Travelling fairs abound in the UK. This is one of the biggest.
Halloween or all hallow's eve	Spooky! But not quite the same as the USA.
Sealth in the UK	The NHS is is the publicly-funded healthcare system of the United Kingdom.
Introductions and greetings	Hi, how are you?
Jarrow crusades	On October 5 th 1936, 200 men set off to London to deliver a petition to protest against unemployment in Britain.
La feill bhride	Otherwise known as St Bride's Day.
Marriage and weddings	British Wedding and Marriage Customs and Traditions
Maundy thursday	Commemorating "The Last Supper".
May day	No not a cry for help but a bank holiday.
Money	The jangly stuff and the folding stuff.
Mother's day	Also known as Mothering Sunday.
New year	First footing?
New year resolutions	Making New Year Resolutions
Nursery rhymes	Some nursery rhymes are a record of our history.
Oak apple day	A day to celebrate British royalty.
Remembrance sunday	A time for peace.
Royal garden parties	More tea?
Rush bearing	Rushbearings are still popular in Cumbria and other parts of north-west England.
Shopping	The changing face of shopping in the UK.
Shrove tuesday	Otherwise known as Pancake Day.
St David's day	The patron saint of Wales.
St George's day	The patron saint of England.
St patrick's day	The patron saint of Ireland.

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St Swithin's day	An interesting bit of folklore all to do with rain.
Stonehenge	The mystery of Stonehenge.
Tea culture in Britain	One lump or two?
Television in Britain	British TV has a long history.
Tolpuddle martyrs	We raise the watchword Liberty, We will, we will, we will be free.
Transport in Britain	British transport - trains and boats and planes.
Trooping the colour	Pageantry - what we are best at.
The union flag	Contrary to popular belief this is not the English flag and it is not usually called the Union Jack.
The United Kingdom	Some facts and figures and a potted history of my homeland.
Valentine's day	A celebration of love.
Work	A tongue in cheek look at working in the UK.
What's on?	A Diary of Events - British customs and traditions.

Locke essentially asserted that a person like a "tabula rasa" ("blank slate"), gains its knowledge from experience. It was in experience that the English philosopher saw the source, limit and foundation of human culture. Experience is interpreted by him quite broadly. Experience consists of the elementary components of knowledge - ideas. The latter means sensations, images, and concepts. Two kinds of ideas (simple and complex) correspond to two kinds of experience - external and internal. External experience is formed as a result of the influence of the external world on us, and internal is the result of understanding the external experience. Therefore, Locke calls internal experience reflection. For the further development of the empirical tradition, Locke's interpretation of external experience, connected with his doctrine of primary and secondary qualities, was of great importance.

R. Bacon - was the forerunner of European experimental science; W. Harvey became the founder of modern physiology and embryology (described the large and small circle of blood circulation); A. Levenhuk invented the microscope;

E. Halley - astronomer and physicist, calculated the orbits of more than 20 comets; D. Priestley discovered oxygen. In the 18th century, S. Johnson, a lexicographer, created the Dictionary of the English Language (1755); D. Hume - formulated the principles of agnosticism; J. Watt invented the steam engine; J. Stephenson - inventor of the steam locomotive; V. Herschel, the founder of stellar astronomy, discovered Uranus.

19th century - M. Faraday became the founder of the doctrine of the electromagnetic field; the evolutionary theory of Charles Darwin became a discovery in world biology; J. Maxwell became the creator of classical electrodynamics; J. Joule experimentally proved the law of conservation of energy;

20th century - G. Rutherford became one of the founders of the doctrine of the radioactivity of the atom; A. Fleming - the microbiologist who discovered penicillin; J. Chadwick - the physicist who discovered the neutron; P. Dirac - one of the founders of quantum mechanics; F. Whittle - inventor of the turbojet engine.

Finally, a new trend emerged from Liverpool in 1962. The Beatles became the most popular musicians of their time, and in the composing duo of John Lennon and Paul McCartney, popularized the concept of the self-contained music act. Before the Beatles, very few popular singers composed the tunes they performed. The "Fab Four" opened the doors for other acts from England such as The Rolling Stones, Genesis, Dire Straits, Iron Maiden, Led Zeppelin, Pink Floyd, Cream, The Kinks, The Who, Eric Clapton, David Bowie, Queen, Elton John, The Hollies, Black Sabbath, Deep Purple, The Police to the globe.

The achievements of British science at the end of the 20th century include: fundamental developments in the field of molecular genetics - the discovery of the three-dimensional structure of DNA by F. Crick, M. Wilkins and D. Watson; S. Hawking's discoveries in the field of the structure and nature of the Universe. The work of British scientists includes the discovery of an ozone hole over Antarctica. The UK government is constantly investing in science and technology and is the second most Nobel Prize laureate in science behind the United States in the world.

In the 19-20th centuries the philosophy of Great Britain is closely related to the most important universities. Most philosophers become teachers and become famous precisely because of this profession. Therefore, the universities of the kingdom - Oxford, Cambridge and others - simultaneously play the role of philosophical centers.

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RESULTS

➤ The culture of England is determined by the cultural norms of England and the British. Due to the influence of England in the United Kingdom, it is sometimes difficult to distinguish English culture from that of the United Kingdom as a whole. However, since Anglo-Saxon times, England has had its own unique culture besides Welsh, Scottish or Northern Irish.

➤ Rich in history, culture and the birthplace of the Industrial Revolution, many of the world's most famous scientists, inventors and thinkers were from England. England has also played an important role in film, literature, technology, engineering, democracy, social studies, and mathematics.

➤ Homes, gardens, rolling hills and green landscapes are common English cultural symbols. The rose and oak are considered the national symbols of England. Humor, tradition and good manners are characteristics commonly associated with English.

CONCLUSION

Concluding the analysis of the culture of England, we can conclude that the culture of this country, while preserving traditions, openly manifests its rationalism, reasonably supplementing it with emotional and sensual ways of world perception, introduced by other cultural worlds.

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